

Effect of Substituents on Rates of Reactions. Part III : Kinetics of Condensation of Substituted Benzaldehydes with Acetone and Ethyl Methyl Ketone

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The rates of base-catalysed condensation of a series of sixteen substituted benzaldehydes with acetone and ethyl methyl ketone were measured colorimetrically. The reaction follows a bimolecular rate law. The plot of $\log k/k_0$ vs $\bar{\sigma}_0$ for the meta substituted compounds was linear and the ρ values at different temperatures were evaluated. The effective sigma values ($\bar{\sigma}$) for various para substituents and calculation of individual inductive (I) and resonance effects (R) of different substituents have been attempted with the help of Taft equation.

IN continuation of our earlier work on the base catalysed condensation of substituted benzaldehydes with cyclohexanone¹, we have studied the effect of substituent in aldehyde moiety on the rate of condensation of various substituted benzaldehydes with acetone and ethyl methyl ketone (EMK). Applicability of Hammett's equation, evaluation of the individual inductive and resonance contributions of the substituents and calculation of the thermodynamic parameters are some of the features not reported earlier.

Experimental

The methods employed for following the rates, determination of $\Delta E^\ddagger$ values and rate law are similar to that reported earlier¹.

Results and Discussion

The mechanism of the condensation reactions consisting of several equilibria as suggested by Noyce *et al.*² may be operative for the reactions studied in the present work. The details of the mechanism has been discussed in our earlier paper¹ on the base catalysed condensation of benzaldehyde and cyclohexanone. From the solvent effect studies³ on the condensation reaction, it was concluded that rate determining step above 75% of ethyl alcohol (v/v) is the reaction between aldehyde and ketone anion.

As seen from Table 1, the rate of condensation of any particular substituted benzaldehyde with acetone is higher compared to its reaction with EMK, in accordance with Price and Hammett's⁴ observation that increase in carbon chain decreases the rate of any reaction.

The structural effects on the rate of condensation are similar to those on the rates of ionisation of

benzoic acid⁵ in the sense that the electron withdrawing substituent groups viz. NO₂, Cl accelerate the reaction while electron donating group viz. OCH₃, CH₃ retard the reaction (Table 1). The order of the reactivity of the substituents is as follows :

The Hammett equation⁶ is applicable to meta substituents fairly well and for para substituents the plot of $\log k/k_0$ versus σ_0 deviate from linear relationship. The prevailing view has been that resonance interactions by the substituents will vary widely from reaction to reaction so that the electronic contribution of the substituents could not possibly be represented by a single constant. Hence, the

effective sigma values ($\bar{\sigma}$) representing the resonance effect for the para substituents are calculated by the use of the equation⁷ $\bar{\sigma} = \frac{\log kp/k_0}{\rho}$. The $\bar{\sigma}$ values are summarised in Table 2. These values for the para substituent groups differ considerably from σ_0 values. The enhanced values indicate substantial increase of resonance interaction between the substituent and the reaction centre in the transition state.

The reaction constant, ρ , has been evaluated by using the select group of meta substituents in benzaldehyde ring and plotting $\log km/k_0$ vs σ_0 values⁷ (Fig. 1 A & B) keeping in view that the meta position in the aromatic system should be relatively insensitive to resonance and steric effects and consequently should be the most favourable position for the inductive effect. The ρ values obtained at the three temperatures (35°, 40° & 45°) along with their correlation coefficients, r , for the reactions studied are

TABLE 1. THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR SUBSTITUTED BENZALDEHYDES AND KETONE REACTION

Substituent in benzaldehyde ring	$k'' \times 10^3$ 1.35 mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	$\Delta E^\ddagger$ cals mole ⁻¹	$\Delta H^\ddagger$ cals mole ⁻¹	$\Delta G^\ddagger$ cals mole ⁻¹	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ e.u.
nil	4.57(2.12)	13730 (13850)	12504 (12624)	21370 (21840)	-28.78 (29.9)
<i>p</i> -NO ₂	236.00(176.7)	9154 (9612)	7938 (8386)	18960 (19130)	-35.8 (-34.9)
<i>m</i> -NO ₂	66.7 (64.5)	9654 (10070)	8428 (8844)	19720 (19840)	-36.64 (-35.7)
<i>m</i> -Cl	22.0 (17.9)	10070 (10070)	8844 (8844)	20420 (20540)	-37.5 (-37.9)
<i>p</i> -Cl	13.9 (9.78)	11440 (10530)	10214 (9304)	20700 (20910)	-34.85 (-37.7)
<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	13.0 (8.7)	10530 (10980)	9304 (9754)	20740 (20980)	-37.14 (-36.4)
<i>m</i> -OH	11.8 (8.3)	10980 (11440)	9754 (10214)	20800 (21010)	-35.87 (-35.1)
<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	4.8 (2.16)	12360 (12316)	11134 (11090)	21330 (21830)	-33.1 (-34.7)
<i>p</i> -OH	3.7 (2.03)	12560 (14640)	11334 (13444)	21500 (21870)	-33.0 (-27.5) _q
<i>p</i> -CH ₃	3.57(2.0)	15516 (13270)	14334 (11944)	21530 (21890)	-23.36 (-32.3)
<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	18.53(11.86)	9654 (9154)	8428 (7928)	20510 (20780)	-39.2 (-41.7) _q
<i>o</i> -Cl	17.5 (2.2)	12910 (12560)	10684 (11334)	25540 (21810)	-31.4 (-33.9)
2,4-dichloro	80.2 (5.67)	10070 (9154)	8844 (7938)	19620 (21230)	-51.2 (-43.2)
2,4-dimethoxy	25.6 (5.67)	8407 (7323)	7181 (6097)	23300 (21230)	-42.6 (-49.1)
2-OCH ₃ , 4-OH	20.3 (7.4)	7323 (9706)	6097 (8480)	20460 (21080)	-46.6 (-40.9)
3-OCH ₃ , 4-OH	6.43(2.84)	9612 (11440)	8426 (10214)	21116(21660)	-41.6 (-37.2)
3,4-dimethoxy	5.57(2.5)	8239 (9840)	7013 (8614)	21240(21740)	-46.2 (-42.6)

The values in the table are for aldehyde and acetone reaction and in parenthesis for aldehyde and ethyl methyl ketone reaction.

The error limits for $\Delta E^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ are ± 0.88 k cal mole⁻¹ and ± 2.7 e.u. respectively.

TABLE 2. EFFECTIVE SIGMA VALUES FOR PARA SUBSTITUENTS.

The values in the table are for aldehyde and acetone reaction and in parenthesis for aldehyde and ethyl methyl ketone reaction

Substituent in benzaldehyde ring	<i>p</i> -OH	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -NO ₂
$\bar{\sigma}$	-0.078 (-0.014)	+0.1746 (+0.0046)	+0.396 (+0.448)	+1.404 (+1.46)
$\bar{\sigma} - \sigma_0$	+0.192 (+0.256)	+0.2946 (+0.125)	+0.126 (+0.178)	+0.584 (+0.646)

given in Table 3. As expected the ρ value decreases with increase in temperature⁸.

The evaluation of the individual contributions due to inductive and resonance effects of a substituent has been attempted by the method given by Taft and Lewis¹⁰, using the equation $\log k/k_0 = I + R$

where $I = \frac{1}{(1-\alpha)} [\log k^m/k_0 - \alpha \log k^p/k_0]_0$ and

$$R = (\log k/k_0 - I) = (\log k/k_0 - \sigma_1 \rho_1)$$

I is inductive effect, R is resonance effect, α is the resonance fall off factor (which is equal to 1/3), σ

Fig. 1. Hammett's Plot of $\log k/k_0$ vs σ
A) for acetone
B) for ethyl methyl ketone

the inductive substituent constant and ρ_1 is the reaction constant for the inductive energy relationship. The I values obtained show the linear inductive energy

TABLE 3. REACTION CONSTANT AND CORRELATION COEFFICIENT AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES

The values in the table are for aldehyde and acetone reaction and in parenthesis for aldehyde and ethyl methyl ketone reaction.

Temp. in °C	ρ	r
35	1.22 (1.48)	0.991 (0.995)
40	1.09 (1.34)	0.987 (0.989)
45	1.04 (1.24)	0.981 (0.985)

relationship with σ_1 values¹⁰. The I values and the values of resonance effects in meta and para positions, R^m & R^p along with the resonance interaction energies $\Delta\Delta G_m$ & $\Delta\Delta G_p$ are summarised in Table 4.

TABLE 4. I , R AND INTERACTION ENERGY VALUES FOR META AND PARA SUBSTITUENTS

Substituent	p -OH	p -OCH ₃	p -Cl	p -NO ₂
I	+0.664 (+0.899)	+0.671 (+0.915)	+0.783 (+0.058)	+0.890 (+1.139)
R^m	-0.252 (-0.300)	-0.216 (-0.303)	-0.100 (-0.132)	+0.275 (+0.221)
R^p	-0.754 (-0.900)	-0.649 (-0.908)	-0.30 (-0.396)	+0.823 (+0.680)
$\Delta\Delta G_m$ k.cal.mole ⁻¹	+0.355 (+0.423)	+0.305 (+0.427)	+0.101 (+0.185)	-0.387 (-0.475)
$\Delta\Delta G_p$ k.cal.mole ⁻¹	+1.064 (+1.257)	+0.915 (+1.280)	+0.423 (+0.781)	-1.161 (-1.424)

The I values represent the total inductive effect contribution to $\log k/k_0$ through σ and π bonds and through space (Field effect) for the meta and para substituents. R values are a measure of total resonance effect. The negative resonance interaction energy values of para nitro group confirms the fact that there is pronounced interaction in the transition state. The positive values for the other para substituents show that they destabilise the transition state.

The thermodynamic parameters for all aldehydes studied (Table 1) may be explained on the basis of iso-kinetic relationship¹² that for the series of compounds of slightly different structure but undergoing reaction essentially by the same mechanism, the $\Delta G^\ddagger$ values may be more or less constant with relative changes in enthalpy of activation ($\Delta H^\ddagger$) and entropy of activation ($\Delta S^\ddagger$). The high negative values of entropy of activation may be due to the bulky aldehyde and ketone anion forming the activated complex. The linear relationship between $\Delta H^\ddagger$ & $\Delta S^\ddagger$ is in accordance with the equation $\Delta H^\ddagger = \Delta H_0^\ddagger + \beta\Delta S^\ddagger$, where, β is the iso-kinetic temperature. The β values for the reactions with acetone and EMK were found to be 400°K and 440°K respectively (Fig. IIA & B). As the temperatures at which the experiments were carried out are well below β values, one could say that it is enthalpy controlled reaction, where the

reaction having lowest activation energy proceeds fast and vice versa, as evident from Table 1.

Fig. II Iso kinetic relationship : Plot of $\Delta H^\ddagger$ vs $\Delta S^\ddagger$

- A) for the reaction between substituted benzaldehydes & acetone.
- B) for the reaction between substituted benzaldehydes & ethyl methyl ketone.

In the case of disubstituted benzaldehyde cumulative effect of the substituents has been observed for $\Delta E^\ddagger$ values for both the condensation reactions. The activation energy of disubstituted benzaldehydes is simply the sum of the activation energies of mono substituted benzaldehydes. This is illustrated as follows :

If the activation energy for benzaldehyde, 2-chloro and 4-chloro benzaldehydes (in benzaldehyde and EMK reaction) are represented as E_1 , E_2 and E_3 respectively, then the activation energy for 2,4-dichlorobenzaldehyde ($\Delta E^\ddagger$) is given by :

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta E^\ddagger &= E + (E_2 - E_1) + (E_3 - E_1) \\ &= 13850 + (-1290) + (-3320) \\ &= 9240 \text{ cal mole}^{-1} \end{aligned}$$

TABLE 5. ACTIVATION ENERGIES OF DISUBSTITUTED BENZALDEHYDES (EXPERIMENTAL AND CALCULATED)

The values in the Tables 4 and 5 are for aldehyde and acetone reaction and in parenthesis for aldehyde and ethyl methyl ketone reaction.

Disubstituted benzaldehyde	$\Delta E^\ddagger$ cals mole ⁻¹ Calculated	$\Delta E^\ddagger$ cals mole ⁻¹ Experimental
2, 4-dichloro	10620(9240)	10070(9154)
3, 4-dimethoxy	9160(10246)	8239(9840)
2, 4-dimethoxy	8284(7620)	8407(7323)
2-OCH ₃ , 4-OH	7484(9944)	7323(9706)
3-OCH ₃ , 4-OH	9360(11890)	9612(1140)

The error limits for $\Delta E^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ are ± 0.88 k.cals.mole⁻¹ and ± 2.7 e.u. respectively.

Experimentally observed $\Delta E^\ddagger = 9154$ cal mole⁻¹. There is thus a good agreement between the experimental value and the calculated one, on the basis of additive effect of substituents for disubstituted (2,4-dichloro) aldehydes. Data for some more disubstituted benzaldehyde is given in Table 5.

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